

Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for Amplicon sequencing of *Plasmodium vivax* (PvAmpSeq) molecular markers

Preparing short amplicons of loci located in chromosome 01, chromosome 02, chromosome 03, chromosome 05, chromosome 07, chromosome 08, chromosome 09, chromosome 10, chromosome 11, chromosome 13 and chromosome 14 of Plasmodium vivax for sequencing on the Illumina iSeq 100 and MiSeq systems.

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This protocol format was adapted from the 16S Metagenomics Sequencing Library Preparation protocol from Illumina.

Introduction and General Overview

Plasmodium vivax causes persistent and recurrent infections, mostly due to relapses of hypnozoites from the liver. To better understand the biology of *P. vivax* it is necessary to determine whether these infections are caused by a relapse or a new infection. Current genetic tools such as length-polymorphic markers (i.e. microsatellites) do not always provide sufficient discriminatory resolution to address this question.

We developed a novel amplicon deep sequencing (PvAmpSeq) tool targeting eleven short but highly polymorphic regions across twelve chromosomes. This tool can be applied in a wide range of epidemiological studies and clinical trials.

The method described in this SOP provides a molecular genotyping system for *Plasmodium vivax* infections. This technology is based on a next-generation sequencing (NGS) protocol referred to as *Plasmodium vivax* amplicon deep sequencing (PvAmpSeq).

Below is a table of molecular markers and their targeted single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and indels in the current PvAmpSeq protocol.

Table 1 Molecular Markers and nucleotide polymorphisms

Molecular marker	Target start	Target end	Gene ID	N variants
Chr_01 - Protein Tyrosine phosphatase putative (PTP2)	612222	612358	PVP01_0113700	6
Chr_02 - Lysophospholipase, putative	62503	62625	PVP01_0201300	11
Chr_03 - conserved Plasmodium protein	129741	129866	PVP01_0302600	9
Chr_05 - STP1 protein	1412445	1412544	PVP01_0533300	5
Chr_07 - merozoite surface protein 1 (MSP1)	1219847	1219964	PVP01_0728900	36
Chr_08 - Plasmodium exported protein	1610537	1610675	PVP01_0838000	9
Chr_09 - Apical Membrane antigen 1 (AMA1)	1459600	1459728	PVP01_0934200	17
Chr_10 - Merozoite surface protein 3 (MSP3.3)	1354022	1354110	PVP01_1031500	15
Chr_11 - Glyoxalase I-like protein (GLIP)	1872223	1872351	PVP01_1144200	6
Chr_13 - conserved Plasmodium protein	2030854	2030957	PVP01_1346800	6
Chr_14 - Reticulocyte binding protein 2a (RBP2a)	114293	114419	PVP01_1402400	14

Materials and Equipment

Please ensure all the necessary user-supplied consumables and equipment are available before proceeding to sample preparation.

Table 2 User-Supplied Consumables

Consumable	Supplier
Non-powdered sterile gloves	General lab supplier
Laboratory coat	General lab supplier
1.5 ml microcentrifuge tubes	General lab supplier
2.5 µl single channel pipettes	General lab supplier
10 µl barrier pipette tips	General lab supplier
10 µl multichannel pipettes	General lab supplier
10 µl single channel pipettes	General lab supplier
20 µl barrier pipette tips	General lab supplier
20 µl multichannel pipettes	General lab supplier
20 µl single channel pipettes	General lab supplier
200 µl barrier pipette tips	General lab supplier
200 µl multichannel pipettes	General lab supplier
200 µl single channel pipettes	General lab supplier
1000 µl barrier pipette tips	General lab supplier
1000 µl single channel pipettes	General lab supplier
PCR grade water	General lab supplier
RNase/DNase-free 8-well PCR strip tubes and caps	Dutscher Catalog # 4ti-0784
[Optional] Disposable Polystyrene Reservoirs	Thomas Scientific Cat # 55501080
GoTaq® Probe qPCR Master Mix	Bio-Rad Catalog #A6102
Microseal 'A' Film	Bio-Rad Catalog # MSA5001
Microseal 'B' Film	Bio-Rad Catalog # MSB1001
96 Multiplicity PCR plate, without skirt	Sarstedt (Fisher) Catalog # 10003852
Kapa HiFi hotstart + dNTP 250U	KAPA Catalog # KK2502 (7958846001)
Amplicon PCR Forward Primer (Standard desalting) (See tables 6-7)	
Amplicon PCR Reverse Primer (Standard desalting) (See tables 6-7)	
qPCR 18sRNA Forward Primer (Standard desalting) (See table 5)	
qPCR 18sRNA Reverse Primer (Standard desalting) (See table 5)	
FrameStar® 384 well PCR plate, frosted wells, clear frame	Dutscher 4TITUDE , Catalog # 45681
Agarose ultrapure	General lab supplier
SYBR™ Safe DNA Gel Stain	ThermoFisher Scientific Catalog # S33102
6X DNA LOADING DYE / 5X 1ml	ThermoFisher Scientific Catalog # R0611
100bp DNA Ladder	ThermoFisher Scientific Catalog # 15628019
UltraPure™ DNA Typing Grade 50 X TAE buffer	ThermoFisher Scientific Catalog # 24710030
Quant-iT™ PicoGreen™ dsDNA Assay Kit (1mL)	Invitrogen/Thermo Fisher Catalog # P7589

Greiner Bio-One FLUOTRAC™ Binding 96-Well Polystyrene Microplates	Fisher Scientific Cat. # 655077 (07-000-127)
Agilent High Sensitivity D5000 ScreenTape	Agilent Technologies, Cat. # 5067-4626 (5067-5592)
Agilent High Sensitivity D5000 Reagents	Agilent Technologies, Cat. # 5067-4626 (5067-5593)
Agilent High Sensitivity D5000 Ladder	Agilent Technologies, Cat. # 5067-4626 (5067-5594)
NucleoMAG NGS Clean up size and select (50mL)	Machery Nagel Catalog #744970.50
Elution Plate, U-bottom (elution plate) (24)	Machery Nagel Catalog #740486.24
Ethanol absolute 1L	Fisher Scientific Catalog #10342652

Table 3 User-Supplied Equipment

Equipment	Supplier
2-8°C Refrigerator	General lab supplier
-20°C Refrigerator	General lab supplier
Vortex	General lab supplier
4x Eppendorf PCR Cooler, iceless cold storage system for 96 well plates and PCR tubes	Sigma-Aldrich, Inc, Cat # Z606634-1EA
QuantStudio TM 5 Real-Time PCR system or equivalent real-time PCR machine	Applied Biosystems, USA, Cat # A28140
96-well thermal cycler (with heated lid)	General lab supplier
Electrophoresis rig	General lab supplier
Magnetic stand-96 or 96S Super Magnet Plate	Life Technologies, Cat # AM10027 or Alpaqua SKU A001322
Microplate centrifuge	General lab supplier
Agilent D4200 ScreenTape System	Agilent Technologies, Catalog # G2991AA

Protocol Workflow

NOTE: The hands-on times are based on using 96-well format plates for each step.

18sRNA DNA TaqMan [Sample QC]

Hands-on time 1 hour / 96 samples | Cycle time 1.5 hours
Reagents: Primers, 2X GoTaq® Probe qPCR Master Mix, DNase PCR free water

Primary PCR [Amplification]

Hands-on time 30 min / 96 samples | Cycle time 1.5 hours
Reagents: 10uM Primers, KAPA HiFi HotStart, 5X KAPA HiFi Fidelity Buffer, 10mM dNTPs, 25mM MgCl₂, DNase PCR free water

Secondary PCR [Amplification]

Hands-on time 30 min / 96 samples | Cycle time 1.5 hours
Reagents: 10uM Primers, KAPA HiFi HotStart, 5X KAPA HiFi Fidelity Buffer, 10mM dNTPs, 25mM MgCl₂, DNase PCR free water

Analysis of PCR amplicons [Electrophoresis]

Hands-on time 40 min / 96 samples; Gel running time 30 min
Reagents: Agarose, SYBR™ Safe DNA Gel Stain, 6X DNA Loading dye, 100bp DNA ladder, 1X TAE Buffer

Amplicon Purification, Quantification, Normalization and Pooling

Hands-on time 80 min / 96 samples; Total time 40+ min/96 samples
Reagents: MinElute 96 UF PCR Purification Plates, Quant-iT™ PicoGreen™ dsDNA Assay Kit, DNase PCR free water, 1X TE Buffer, DNA stock

Library Amplification

Hands-on time 40 min / 96 samples | Cycle time 30 min / 96 samples
Reagents: 10uM Primers, KAPA HiFi HotStart, 5X KAPA HiFi Fidelity Buffer, 10mM dNTPs, DNase PCR free water

Library Quantification, Normalization and Pooling

Hands-on time 40 min / 96 samples; Total time 40+ min/96 samples
Reagents: Quant-iT™ PicoGreen™ dsDNA Assay Kit, DNase PCR free water, 1X TE Buffer, DNA stock

Library Pool Cleaning up, Quantification and Size verification

Reagents: NucleoMag® NGS Clean-up and Size Select; Quant-iT™ PicoGreen™ dsDNA Assay Kit, DNase PCR free water, 1X TE Buffer, DNA stock; Sample Buffer, D5000 Ladder, ScreenTape

iSeq/MiSeq Sample Loading

Hands on time 30 min / pooled samples; Total time 30 min / pooled samples
Reagents: Resuspension Buffer, HT1, 0.2N NaOH, PhiX Control Kit v3, 200mM Tris-HCl pH7.0

Analysis of NGS data [Analysis]

Total time 2 hours / 96 samples
Method: AmpSeqR
Please visit for directions: <https://github.com/bahlolab/AmpSeqR>

1. QC of DNA samples: qPCR to confirm amplifiable parasite DNA

This assay aims to detect the presence of *Plasmodium vivax* gDNA in a DNA extract. It relies on the amplification and detection of a fragment of the 18sRNA DNA using a combination of primers and probes specific for *P. vivax*. It is a TaqMan qPCR assay.

Consumables

Table 4. 18sRNA DNA TaqMan Consumables

Item	Quantity	Storage
18S <i>P. vivax</i> primers (see below)	0.25 µL per sample	2° to 8° C
18S Pv-probe	1.00 µL per sample	2° to 8° C
Nuclease-free water	3.25 µL per sample	Room temperature
10 ⁶ copies/µl Pv plasmid		-20° to -30° C
FrameStar® 384 well PCR plate, frosted wells, clear frame		Room temperature
Tube centrifuge 15ml Polystyrene		Room temperature
Filter tips 10XL, 200µl and 1000µL		Room temperature
Single-channel pipettes: 20-200µl and 100-1000µl		Room temperature
Multichannel pipette: 1-10µl		Room temperature

Preparation

- All stock primers should be prepared at a 10µM concentration.
- DNA samples should be stored at 4°C until testing or -20°C for long term storage.
- Store all primer stocks at -20°C for up to 1 year.
- Unopened tubes of 1X GoTaq® Probe qPCR Master Mix (Promega, USA) should be stored at -20°C for a maximum of six months. The reagent must be used within the expiration date provided by the manufacturer.
- Samples should be tested in duplicates in some particular cases (e.g. very low-density situations).

Positive controls: (Freezer, -20°C)

From an aliquot of 10⁶ copies/µl Pv plasmid, prepare the following dilutions by diluting the plasmid with TE buffer or PCR water. Briefly vortex and microcentrifuge each tube prior to opening it.

Dilutions for each plasmids:

Standard	DNA concentration (ng/µL)	PCR H2O	Volume of DNA solution
S1	10 ⁵ copies/ µL	45 µL	5 µL of 10 ⁶ copies/ µL
S2	10 ⁴ copies/ µL	45 µL	5 µL of 10 ⁵ copies/ µL
S3	10 ³ copies/ µL	45 µL	5 µL of 10 ⁴ copies/ µL
S4	10 ² copies/ µL	45 µL	5 µL of 10 ³ copies/ µL
S5	10 copies/ µL	45 µL	5 µL of 10 ² copies/ µL

S6	5 copies/ μ L	25 μ L	25 μ L of 10 copies/ μ L
S7	1 copy/ μ L	40 μ L	10 μ L of 5 copies/ μ L
Blank	Blank	-	

NB: The probe is light-sensitive – limit exposure to light. Don't thaw/freeze an aliquot of probe more than 3 times as probe degradation might occur and result in a loss of sensitivity of the reaction. The GoTaq® Probe qPCR Master Mix contains a hot start Taq DNA polymerase (requires heat activation).

Procedure

Initial Set up

- Remove the tubes of reagents from the freezer/fridge and place them in a rack on the Master Mix bench. Avoid light exposure of the probe. When thawed, briefly vortex and centrifuge the reagents to concentrate the liquid at the bottom of the tubes.
- The qPCR reaction mix is prepared by mixing the GoTaq® Probe qPCR Master Mix, primers, and water, as indicated in Table 5.
- Determine the number of reactions you need to run by multiplying the total number of samples you have to test (including your positive and negative controls) + 10% (for user pipetting errors).
- In a 15mL Falcon tube, prepare your master-mix by multiplying the volumes indicated in Table 5 with the total number of reactions you need to run.

Primers and PCR conditions

Table 5. *P. vivax* 18sRNA DNA master mix

<i>P. vivax</i> 18sRNA DNA (216bp)	Volume	X samples * 1.1	Final [conc]
H ₂ O	3.25 μ L		
2X GoTaq® Probe qPCR Master Mix	6.50 μ L		1 x
18SPv F / R primer (10 μ M)	0.25 μ L		0.769 μ M
18SPv-probe (10 μ M)	1.0 μ L		0.384 μ M
Total	11.0 μL		
Add			
gDNA	2 μ L/well	-	
TOTAL	13.0 μL		

Thermal cycling conditions		45 X
95°	2:00 min	
95°	0:15 min	
58°	1:00 min	

Primers:

18SPv-1F: 5-GCTTTGTAATTGGAATGATGGGAAT-3

18SPv-1R: 5-ATGCGCACAAAGTCGATACGAAG-3

18SPv-probe: 5-[HEX] AGCAACGCTTCTAGCTTA [MGB-NFQ]-3

Adding the DNA Samples

- 1 Mix the prepared master-mix well by vortexing briefly.
- 2 Centrifuge the tubes for 5 seconds to remove any solution trapped in the cap.
- 3 Arrange the optically clear PCR tubes on a PCR-tube rack following the PCR sample sheet. Add 11 μ l of the master mix prepared above to each PCR well. Loosely put on the lids of the wells filled with master mix solution.

- 4 Return all reagents to the freezer and refrigerator before proceeding to the next step.
- 5 Take the assembled plate containing the tubes with PCR master mix solution to the PCR template area.
- 6 Add 2µl of the unknown DNA samples to the wells with the master-mix according to the sample sheet. Cap the well tightly after adding the sample. The total volume of PCR reaction is 13.0 µl after addition of the template.
- 7 Add positive control DNA to each positive control well with master-mix. Cap the wells after each positive control are added.
- 8 Add 2.0 µl of DNase-free H₂O to the wells designated as the no-template control (NTC) and close that well tightly.
- 9 Make sure each sample has been added to the correct well and that all wells are tightly capped.
- 10 Centrifuge for 30sec-1 min at 2000 rpm to remove any solution trapped on the walls of the wells. Visually inspect plate for the presence of bubbles – if bubbles, centrifuge again. If no bubbles, cover sealed plate with aluminium foil and transport to QuantStudio™ 5 Real-Time PCR instrument.

NOTE: *The amount of template DNA to be used can be as low as 2µL, but it is not uncommon to use 4µL. This can be adjusted appropriately depending on the sample parasitemia. The change should be discussed before it is implemented.*

PCR-Cycling Parameters

- 1 Start the real-time PCR thermocycler according to the manufacturer’s guidelines.
- 2 Program the software to detect fluorescence through HEX and ROX filters all wells. ROX is to be detected as a reference dye.
- 3 Program the software to run the cycling conditions shown on page 7.
- 4 Fluorescence data should be collected at the amplification plateau.

Interpreting Results

- 1 If the calculated thresholds are located within the background noise, they should be manually set to a level slightly higher than the background. Such alterations should be done with only one dye displayed at the time.
- 2 Positive specimens are those that yield a fluorescence signal above the threshold value in the wells where samples or controls were loaded.
 - a. Positive PCR: A positive sample produces a fluorescence signal above the threshold/noise level. Positive samples are designated a Ct value below 40.0.
 - b. Negative PCR: No fluorescence signal above the threshold/noise level. Negative samples have no Ct or have a Ct value above 40.0.
- 3 Estimate a linear equation by extrapolating the standard curve Ct and corresponding copy number values.
- 4 Calculate the copy numbers of 18sRNA using the following equation.

$$\frac{\text{Copy number}}{\mu\text{L}} = \left(\frac{\text{Ct} - \text{slope}}{\text{intercept}} \right)$$

NOTE: *The negative controls must be negative (no Ct or above 40.0). The positive controls must be positive (designated by Ct value below 40.0). The test should be repeated if the NTC has a positive Ct value, or if the positive control yields no positive results.*

For more information, please see:

Rosanas-Urgell A, Mueller D, Betuela I, Barnadas C, Iga J, Zimmerman PA, del Portillo HA, Mueller I, Felger I. Comparison of diagnostic methods for the detection and quantification of the four sympatric *Plasmodium* species in field samples from Papua New Guinea. *Malaria J*, 2010, 9(1):361.

2. Gene PCR enrichment by Primary PCR

This step uses PCR to amplify template from a DNA sample using region of interest-specific primers. User-defined forward and reverse primers are used to amplify templates from genomic DNA.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of Gene PCR enrichment by Primary and Secondary PCR. gDNA: Parasite genomic DNA. pDNA: Primary PCR product. Marker primers: Specific primers with an overhang sequence in the 5' ends.

Procedure

Initial Set up

- Ensure that the No-DNA and DNA-only UV stations have all the appropriate pipettes and tip sizes.
- Clean up all pipettes and lab bench area using 10% bleach, followed by 70% ethanol.
- Turn on the No-DNA (PCR master mix) and DNA-only UV station for 15 minutes.
- If you have not already done so, create a 10uM working stock solution of your primers, using $C1V1 = C2V2$ to calculate the appropriate volume needed to make a working stock solution.
- Label all freshly made and newly opened items with the date and your name initials.
- Get the appropriate number of PCR plates and/or PCR tubes and place them in the no-DNA UV station.
- Label the PCR tubes (use a printout template for PCR plates) with sample IDs.
- Get the appropriate number Eppendorf PCR Cooler plates from the freezer, wipe down with 70% ethanol and place them in the UV hoods (one or more sets each in the no-DNA and DNA-only UV stations).
- Be sure to reserve the appropriate number of thermocyclers and have the appropriate cycling conditions set up (**Table 6**).

Step by step procedure

- Let Primers, dNTPs, and HiFi Buffer defrost at room temperature (10-15 min). Once defrosted, mix gently (vortexed) and centrifuge briefly prior to use. DO NOT thaw and/or vortex or mix the KAPA HiFi HotStart.
 - All PCR reactions must be assembled on the Eppendorf PCR Cooler plates
 - Always add the HotStart last when making your master mix and DO NOT vortex and/or pipette after adding HotStart.
 - If you forget to return any of the reagents, especially the HotStart, to its appropriate storage conditions (i.e., leave it out at room temperature), record the date and time of when it happened, and discard.
- 1 Set up the following reaction of water, 5X KAPA HiFi Buffer Fidelity, dNTPs, primers, KAPA HiFi HotStart, and DNA in the order given in **Tables 6.1 – 6.6**:

- Calculate appropriate volumes for master mix based on the number of samples to be included in reaction; multiply each reagent volume by the total number of samples + 10% (for user pipetting errors).

- The final volume of the master mix is given in **Tables 6.1 - 6.6**

NOTE: If the number of samples is <5, make a master mix for at least 6 samples to avoid pipetting volume errors.

- 2 Seal plates and/or PCR tubes.
- 3 Once tubes and/or plates are sealed, keep them in the Eppendorf PCR Cooler plates. **Pre-heat** the thermal cycler to 98 °C prior to placing PCR plates and/or PCR tubes into the thermal cycler. Pre-heating to 98 °C should take 0:30 of the 3:00 min.

Primers and PCR conditions

The tables below show primers and PCR conditions for Chr 05/ Chr 07/ Chr 13/ Chr 14 multiplex (6.1), Chr 01/ Chr 03 / Chr 08 multiplex (6.2), Chr 02/ Chr 09/ Chr 10/ Chr 11 multiplex (6.3), Chr 04 (6.4) and Chr 06 (6.5).

Table 6.1 Mix A: Chr 05 - STP1 protein/ Chr 07 - MSP1/ Chr 13 - conserved Plasmodium protein /Chr 14 - RBP2a

<i>Chr 05 (194bp)/Chr 07 (463bp)/Chr 13 (208 bp)/Chr 14 (297bp)</i>	Volume	X samples * 1.1	Final [conc]
H ₂ O	7.65 µL		
5X KAPA HiFi Buffer Fidelity	6.00 µL		1.2 x
dNTP (10 mM)	0.75 µL		0.3 mM
MgCl ₂ (25 Mm)	1.00 µL		1 mM
F Primer Chr_05 (10 µM)	0.63 µL		0.25 µM
R Primer Chr_05 (10 µM)	0.63 µL		0.25 µM
F Primer Chr_07 (10 µM)	0.43 µL		0.17 µM
R Primer Chr_07 (10 µM)	0.43 µL		0.17 µM
F Primer Chr_13 (10 µM)	0.58 µL		0.23 µM
R Primer Chr_13 (10 µM)	0.58 µL		0.23 µM
F Primer Chr_14 (10 µM)	0.43 µL		0.17 µM
R Primer Chr_14 (10 µM)	0.43 µL		0.17 µM
KAPA HiFi HotStart (1U/µL)	0.50 µL		0.02 units
Total	20.0 µL		
Add			
gDNA	5 µL/well	-	
TOTAL	25.0 µL		

Thermal cycling conditions	
95°	3:00 min
98°	0:20 min
58°	0:20 min
72°	0:30 min
72°	3:00 min
4°	∞

25 X

Primers: PvP01_05_v1_OutF: TATTAAGTATTCATATTCTATGTCTCGC; **PvP01_05_v1_OutR:** TTTTATGCCATTTGTTCCCATTAAC

Primers: PvP01_07_v1_OutF: ACCCATACAAGCTGCTCGAC; **PvP01_07_v1_OutR:** TCCTCCAACCTTCATCCATC

Primers: PvP01_13_v1_OutF: GAATGAGCTGTGTAGAATTTAATTTGT; **PvP01_13_v1_OutR:** CATAATGTAAAACTGTACGTAATGT

Primers: PvP01_14_v1_OutF: ACCCAGAGAATCACAATATAAACCT; **PvP01_14_v1_OutR:** ACCCCCAATTGGAGAGATGC

Table 6.2 Mix B: Chr 01 - PTP2 protein/ Chr 03 - conserved Plasmodium protein /Chr 08 - Plasmodium exported protein

<i>Chr 01 (453bp)/Chr 03 (264bp)/Chr 08 (404bp)</i>	Volume	X samples * 1.1	Final [conc]
<i>H₂O</i>	7.88 µL		
<i>5X KAPA HiFi Buffer Fidelity</i>	4.80 µL		1.2x
<i>dNTP (10 mM)</i>	0.60 µL		0.3 mM
<i>F Primer Chr_01 (10 µM)</i>	0.44 µL		0.22 µM
<i>R Primer Chr_01 (10 µM)</i>	0.44 µL		0.22 µM
<i>F Primer Chr_03 (10 µM)</i>	0.44 µL		0.22 µM
<i>R Primer Chr_03 (10 µM)</i>	0.44 µL		0.22 µM
<i>F Primer Chr_08 (10 µM)</i>	0.28 µL		0.14 µM
<i>R Primer Chr_08 (10 µM)</i>	0.28 µL		0.14 µM
<i>KAPA HiFi HotStart (1U/µL)</i>	0.40 µL		0.02 units
Total	16.0 µL		
Add			
gDNA	4 µL/well	-	
TOTAL	20.0 µL		

Thermal cycling conditions	
95°	3:00 min
98°	0:20 min
53°	0:20 min
72°	0:30 min
25 X	
72°	3:00 min
4°	∞

Primers: PvP01_01_v1_OutF: AGTACTTTCCAGGGACGCTC; **PvP01_01_v1_OutR:** CTCCTAGATGGCCGCTTACT

Primers: PvP01_03_v1_OutF: AAGCTTTATTACGTGGCCGATGA; **PvP01_03_v1_OutR:** TTATAAAAAACAAACGGAGGAAAAAGGCA

Primers: PvP01_08_v1_OutF: GCTGTGCTTAGTATGTTTTAGGGA; **PvP01_08_v1_OutR:** GCACCGCGCTCAATATGTACA

Table 6.3 Mix C: Chr 02 - lysophospholipase/Chr 09 - AMA1/Chr 10 - MSP3.3/Chr 11 - GLIP

<i>Chr 02 (243bp)/Chr 09 (358bp)/Chr 10 (238bp)/Chr 11 (403bp)</i>	Volume	X samples * 1.1	Final [conc]
H ₂ O	8.85 µL		
5X KAPA HiFi Buffer Fidelity	6.00 µL		1.2 x
dNTP (10 mM)	0.75 µL		0.3 mM
F Primer Chr_02 (10 µM)	0.55 µL		0.22 µM
R Primer Chr_02 (10 µM)	0.55 µL		0.22 µM
F Primer Chr_09 (10 µM)	0.40 µL		0.16 µM
R Primer Chr_09 (10 µM)	0.40 µL		0.16 µM
F Primer Chr_10 (10 µM)	0.55 µL		0.22 µM
R Primer Chr_10 (10 µM)	0.55 µL		0.22 µM
F Primer Chr_11 (10 µM)	0.48 µL		0.19 µM
R Primer Chr_11 (10 µM)	0.48 µL		0.19 µM
KAPA HiFi HotStart (1U/µL)	0.50 µL		0.02 units
Total	20.0 µL		
Add			
gDNA	5 µL/well	-	
TOTAL	25.0 µL		

Thermal cycling conditions	
95°	3:00 min
98°	0:20 min
53°	0:20 min
72°	0:30 min
72°	3:00 min
4°	∞

25 X

Primers: PvP01_02_v2_OutF: AGGCAAAGGAATCTGGCTTAG; **PvP01_02_v2_OutR:** AAGCATTCAACTCGAAGGGT

Primers: PvP01_09_v1_OutF: CATCGAAAGAACACACAGTTCT; **PvP01_09_v1_OutR:** TGGGTGCTCTAGGACGAATTTT

Primers: PvP01_10_v2.2_OutF: GTGCAAATGCGCTGCTACAT; **PvP01_10_v2.2_OutR:** GCCATGTTGTGTCATCCCT

Primers: PvP01_11_v1_OutF: TTTTACAAAAATGTGCTGGGTTTTCA; **PvP01_11_v1_OutR:** CGTGATCGGCCTTTTGTCTAT

SAFE STOPPING POINT. If you do not immediately proceed to Secondary PCR, seal plate with adhesive seal and store it at 2° to 8°C for up to a week.

3. Gene PCR enrichment by Secondary PCR

This step uses PCR to amplify template from a primary PCR product using region of interest-specific primers. This amplification step is performed using specific primers with an overhang sequence in the 5' ends. These overhang enables multiplexing of amplicons per sample.

Primers and PCR conditions

The tables below show primers and PCR conditions for Chr 05 (7.1), Chr 07 (7.2), Chr 13 (7.3), Chr 14 (7.4), Chr 01 (7.5), Chr 03 (7.6), Chr 08 (7.7), Chr 02 (7.8), Chr 09 (7.9), Chr 10 (7.10), Chr 11 (7.11), and Chr 04 (7.12) nested.

Table 7.1 Nested PCR Chr 05 - STP1 protein

<i>Chr 05 (188bp)</i>	Volume	X samples * 1.1	Final [conc]
<i>H₂O</i>	12.5 µL		
<i>5X KAPA HiFi Fidelity Buffer</i>	5 µL		1 x
<i>dNTP (10 mM)</i>	0.75 µL		0.3 mM
<i>F Primer (10 µM)</i>	0.625 µL		0.25 µM
<i>R Primer (10 µM)</i>	0.625 µL		0.25 µM
<i>Kapa HiFi HotStart (1U/µL)</i>	0.5 µL		0.02 units
Total	20.0 µL		
Add			
Primary PCR product Mix A	5 µL/well		
TOTAL	25.0 µL		

Thermal cycling conditions	
95°	3:00 min
98°	0:20 min
58.8°	0:20 min
72°	0:30 min
72°	3:00 min
4°	∞

25 X

Primers: PVP01_0533300_Inn_1F: GTGACCTATGAACTCAGGAGTCCGCACTGGTACGTCCAAACTAT;
PVP01_0533300_Inn_1R: CTGAGACTTGACATCGCAGCGCAGTACACCTCCTTAGGATCT

Table 7.2 Nested PCR Chr 07 - MSP1

<i>Chr 07 (194bp)</i>	Volume	X samples * 1.1	Final [conc]
<i>H₂O</i>	12.5 µL		
<i>5X KAPA HiFi Fidelity Buffer</i>	5 µL		1 x
<i>dNTP (10 mM)</i>	0.75 µL		0.3 mM
<i>F Primer (10 µM)</i>	0.625 µL		0.25 µM
<i>R Primer (10 µM)</i>	0.625 µL		0.25 µM
<i>Kapa HiFi HotStart (1U/µL)</i>	0.5 µL		0.02 units
Total	20.0 µL		
Add			
Primary PCR product Mix A	5 µL/well		
TOTAL	25.0 µL		

Thermal cycling conditions	
95°	3:00 min
98°	0:20 min
55.7°	0:20 min
72°	0:30 min
72°	3:00 min
4°	∞

25 X

Primers: PVP01_0728900_InnF: GTGACCTATGAACTCAGGAGTCGAGCTCTACAAGACGCACTT;
PVP01_0728900_InnR: CTGAGACTTGACATCGCAGCCTCCARCTCGGCCTTTTT

Table 7.3 Nested PCR Chr 13 - Plasmodium exported protein

<i>Chr 13 (202bp)</i>	Volume	X samples * 1.1	Final [conc]
H ₂ O	11.5 µL		
5X KAPA HiFi Fidelity Buffer	5 µL		1 x
dNTP (10 mM)	0.75 µL		0.3 mM
MgCl ₂ (25 mM)	1 µL		1 mM
F Primer (10 µM)	0.625 µL		0.25 µM
R Primer (10 µM)	0.625 µL		0.25 µM
Kapa HiFi HotStart (1U/µL)	0.5 µL		0.02 units
Total	20.0 µL		
Add			
Primary PCR product Mix A	5 µL/well		
TOTAL	25.0 µL		

Thermal cycling conditions	
95°	3:00 min
98°	0:20 min
57°	0:20 min
72°	0:30 min
72°	3:00 min
4°	∞

25 X

Primers: PVP01_1346800_Inn_1F: GTGACCTATGAACTCAGGAGTCGTCGTTGCCTCATGTGACAAAT;
PVP01_1346800_Inn_1R: CTGAGACTTGCACATCGCAGCGTCCATTTTGTGGATATTCGAAAAAA

Table 7.4 Nested PCR Chr 14 - Reticulocyte binding protein 2a (RBP2a)

<i>Chr 14 (220bp)</i>	Volume	X samples * 1.1	Final [conc]
H ₂ O	12.5 µL		
5X KAPA HiFi Buffer Fidelity	5 µL		1 x
dNTP (10 mM)	0.75 µL		0.3 mM
F Primer (10 µM)	0.625 µL		0.25 µM
R Primer (10 µM)	0.625 µL		0.25 µM
Kapa HiFi HotStart (1U/µL)	0.5 µL		0.02 units
Total	20.0 µL		
Add			
Primary PCR product Mix A	5 µL/well		
TOTAL	25.0 µL		

Thermal cycling conditions	
95°	3:00 min
98°	0:20 min
63°	0:20 min
72°	0:30 min
72°	3:00 min
4°	∞

25 X

Primers: PVP01_1402400_Inn_1F: GTGACCTATGAACTCAGGAGTCAAGCATAATGAGTACAAGCAGC;
PVP01_1402400_Inn_1R: CTGAGACTTGCACATCGCAGCATATATTCAAGCATAATTCGTACGTA

Table 7.5 Nested PCR Chr 01 - Protein Tyrosine phosphatase putative (PTP2)

<i>Chr 01 (223bp)</i>	Volume	X samples * 1.1	Final [conc]
H ₂ O	11.5 µL		
5X KAPA HiFi Buffer Fidelity	6 µL		1.2 x
dNTP (10 mM)	0.75 µL		0.3 mM
F Primer (10 µM)	0.625 µL		0.25 µM
R Primer (10 µM)	0.625 µL		0.25 µM
Kapa HiFi HotStart (1U/µL)	0.5 µL		0.02 units
Total	20.0 µL		
Add			
Primary PCR product Mix C	5 µL/well		
TOTAL	25.0 µL		

Thermal cycling conditions	
95°	3:00 min
98°	0:20 min
59°	0:20 min
72°	0:30 min
72°	3:00 min
4°	∞

25 X

Primers: PVP01_0113700_Inn_1F: GTGACCTATGAACTCAGGAGTCCCCTTGTTGCAATGCACAAGGA;
PVP01_0113700_Inn_1R: CTGAGACTTGCACATCGCAGCTAACATGGCAGGGGAGGAGTG

Table 7.6 Nested PCR Chr 03 - conserved Plasmodium protein

<i>Chr 03 (214bp)</i>	Volume	X samples * 1.1	Final [conc]
H ₂ O	11.5 µL		
5X KAPA HiFi Fidelity Buffer	6 µL		1.2 x
dNTP (10 mM)	0.75 µL		0.3 mM
F Primer (10 µM)	0.625 µL		0.25 µM
R Primer (10 µM)	0.625 µL		0.25 µM
Kapa HiFi HotStart (1U/µL)	0.5 µL		0.02 units
Total	20.0 µL		
Add			
Primary PCR product Mix B	5 µL/well		
TOTAL	25.0 µL		

Thermal cycling conditions	
95°	3:00 min
98°	0:20 min
61°	0:20 min
72°	0:30 min
72°	3:00 min
4°	∞

25 X

Primers: PVP01_0302600_Inn_1F: GTGACCTATGAACTCAGGAGTCCACGTTATGGGGCTGATGTGTA;
PVP01_0302600_Inn_1R: CTGAGACTTGCACATCGCAGCCCCGATTATACTCGCGGAGGATA

Table 7.7 Nested PCR Chr 08 - Plasmodium exported protein

<i>Chr 08 (221bp)</i>	Volume	X samples * 1.1	Final [conc]
H ₂ O	11.5 µL		
5X KAPA HiFi Fidelity Buffer	6 µL		1.2 x
dNTP (10 mM)	0.75 µL		0.3 mM
F Primer (10 µM)	0.625 µL		0.25 µM
R Primer (10 µM)	0.625 µL		0.25 µM
Kapa HiFi HotStart (1U/µL)	0.5 µL		0.02 units
Total	20.0 µL		
Add			
Primary PCR product Mix B	5 µL/well		
TOTAL	25.0 µL		

Thermal cycling conditions		
95°	3:00 min	
98°	0:20 min	15 X
61°	0:20 min	
72°	0:30 min	
98°	0:20 min	10X
63°	0:20 min	
72°	0:30 min	
72°	3:00 min	
4°	∞	

Primers: PVP01_0838000_Inn_1F: GTGACCTATGAACTCAGGAGTCCACTTACTACGCGGTGCCCA;
PVP01_0838000_Inn_1R: CTGAGACTTGACATCGCAGCTGTGCATGAAACGAAGCCTAC

Table 7.8 Nested PCR Chr 02 - Lysophospholipase, putative

<i>Chr 02 (212bp)</i>	Volume	X samples * 1.1	Final [conc]
H ₂ O	12.65 µL		
5X KAPA HiFi Buffer Fidelity	5 µL		1 x
dNTP (10 mM)	0.75 µL		0.3 mM
F Primer (10 µM)	0.55 µL		0.22 µM
R Primer (10 µM)	0.55 µL		0.22 µM
Kapa HiFi HotStart (1U/µL)	0.5 µL		0.02 units
Total	20.0 µL		
Add			
Primary PCR product Mix C	5 µL/well		
TOTAL	25.0 µL		

Thermal cycling conditions		
95°	3:00 min	
98°	0:20 min	25 X
67°	0:20 min	
72°	0:30 min	
72°	3:00 min	
4°	∞	

Primers: PVP01_0201300_Inn_1F: GTGACCTATGAACTCAGGAGTCTATGCACCCCTTCAAATTAATACT;
PVP01_0201300_Inn_1R: CTGAGACTTGACATCGCAGCTAAAGAAAGAGGTACGCTGCCT

Table 7.9 Nested PCR Chr 09 - Apical Membrane antigen 1 (AMA1)

<i>Chr 09 (222bp)</i>	Volume	X samples * 1.1	Final [conc]
H ₂ O	12.65 µL		
5X KAPA HiFi Buffer Fidelity	5 µL		1 x
dNTP (10 mM)	0.75 µL		0.3 mM
F Primer (10 µM)	0.55 µL		0.22 µM
R Primer (10 µM)	0.55 µL		0.22 µM
Kapa HiFi HotStart (1U/µL)	0.5 µL		0.02 units
Total	20.0 µL		
Add			
Primary PCR product Mix C	5 µL/well		
TOTAL	25.0 µL		

Thermal cycling conditions	
95°	3:00 min
98°	0:20 min
60°	0:20 min
72°	0:30 min
72°	3:00 min
4°	∞

25 X

Primers: PVP01_0934200_Inn1F: GTGACCTATGAACTCAGGAGTCTCCTGTTTTGGAAAGGGTATCG;
PVP01_0934200_Inn1R: CTGAGACTTGCACATCGCAGCATCATCTCTACATTGCTTTTATACCTTT

Table 7.10 Nested PCR Chr 10 - Merozoite surface protein 3 (MSP3.3)

<i>Chr 10 (174bp)</i>	Volume	X samples * 1.1	Final [conc]
H ₂ O	12.5 µL		
5X KAPA HiFi Buffer Fidelity	5 µL		1 x
dNTP (10 mM)	0.75 µL		0.3 mM
F Primer (10 µM)	0.625 µL		0.25 µM
R Primer (10 µM)	0.625 µL		0.25 µM
Kapa HiFi HotStart (1U/µL)	0.5 µL		0.02 units
Total	20.0 µL		
Add			
Primary PCR product Mix C	5 µL/well		
TOTAL	25.0 µL		

Thermal cycling conditions	
95°	3:00 min
98°	0:20 min
60°	0:20 min
72°	0:30 min
72°	3:00 min
4°	∞

25 X

Primers: PVP01_1031500_Inn2F: GTGACCTATGAACTCAGGAGTCAACAGACTGAACGCAAAAACAG;
PVP01_1031500_Inn2R: CTGAGACTTGCACATCGCAGCCACAAAACAGTGGGAAGAGGG

Table 7.11 Nested PCR Chr 11 - Glyoxalase I-like protein (GLIP)

<i>Chr 11 (215bp)</i>	Volume	X samples * 1.1	Final [conc]
<i>H₂O</i>	12.75 μ L		
<i>5X KAPA HiFi Buffer Fidelity</i>	5 μ L		1 x
<i>dNTP (10 mM)</i>	0.75 μ L		0.3 mM
<i>F Primer (10 μM)</i>	0.50 μ L		0.20 μ M
<i>R Primer (10 μM)</i>	0.50 μ L		0.20 μ M
<i>Kapa HiFi HotStart (1U/μL)</i>	0.5 μ L		0.02 units
Total	20.0 μL		
Add			
Primary PCR product Mix C	5 μ L/well		
TOTAL	25.0 μL		

Thermal cycling conditions		
95°	3:00 min	
98°	0:20 min	25 X
61°	0:20 min	
72°	0:30 min	
72°	3:00 min	
4°	∞	

Primers: PV01_1144200_Inn1F: GTGACCTATGAACTCAGGAGTCCTGTAGGAGAGGTATCTTCGCC;
PV01_1144200_Inn1R: CTGAGACTTGACATCGCAGCAGGTGGGGAAAAAGGGTTTGC

SAFE STOPPING POINT. If you do not immediately proceed to Electrophoresis, seal plate with adhesive seal and store it at 4°C.

4. Analysis of PCR amplicons [Electrophoresis]

Consumables

Table 7. Electrophoresis Consumables

Item	Quantity	Storage
Agarose	1.5 g (for a 1.5% gel)	Room temperature
1X TAE buffer	100 mL (for a 1.5% gel)	Room temperature
SYBR® Safe (10'000 X)	10 µL per 100 mL of buffer	Room temperature
0.5 µg/mL Ethidium Bromide	2 µL per 100 mL of buffer	Room temperature
6X Loading buffer	2 µL per 4 µL PCR product	Room temperature
PCR water	4 µL per 4 µL PCR product	Room temperature

Preparation

- Create a 1X solution of 10X TAE Buffer and deionized water before you start.

Procedure

- 1 **NB:** You should always wear gloves for protection of intercalant substances like SYBR Safe or Ethidium bromide. Choose an Erlenmeyer flask that is 2-4 times the volume of the solution and place a stirring rod into the flask.
- 2 Weigh 1.5 gram of agarose + 100 mL of 1X TAE buffer. Note: 1X TBE buffer can be used without any difference in migration.
- 3 Dissolve the agar in the microwave by heating the solution on high power until it comes to a boil. Watch the solution closely (no transparent agarose clumps should be present). **DO NOT** allow the solution to boil over.
- 4 Allow the solution to cool on a stirring plate until you can comfortably hold the flask with your hands.
- 5 Using a 10 µl pipette, add nucleic acid gel stain to the solution. For every 100 mL of the buffer, add 10 µl of 10'000X SYBR® Safe. Alternatively to SYBR Safe, add 1 uL of 0.5 µg/mL Ethidium Bromide. Swirl solution to mix, making sure as little bubbles as possible are created.
- 6 Pour the cooled solution into the gel form- ensure no bubbles are present. Place the comb into the gel and allow the gel to sit undisturbed for at least 15 minutes or until the gel has become firm (the colour will change from clear to slightly milky in colour).
- 7 In a clean PCR plate, mix 4 µL of PCR product + 2 µL of 6X Loading buffer + 6 µL of PCR water.
- 8 Run the gel for about 45 minutes -until the samples nearly reach the end of the gel. **DO NOT** allow samples to run off the gel.
- 9 Turn off the power supply, disconnect the electrodes, and remove the lid.
- 10 Remove the gel from the chamber and take to the gel reading station for analysis.
- 11 Once amplification is confirmed, proceed with quantification, normalization and pooling of PCR products. See an example in figure 2.

Figure 2. Example of Nested PCR products for markers Chr 03, Chr 05, Chr 07, and Chr 08. DNA Ladder: 100 bp .

5. MinElute 96 UF PCR Purification

The QIAGEN MinElute 96 UF PCR Purification Kit combines the convenience of multiwell technology and the separation properties of an ultrafiltration membrane with a unique design. The plates enable the fast and efficient recovery of double-stranded DNA fragments ≥ 100 bp and the removal of primers (<20mers), unincorporated nucleotides, and salts. PCR products are applied to the wells of the ultrafiltration plate and a vacuum is applied. While small molecules such as primers, salts, and unincorporated nucleotides run through the membrane, PCR products are retained. Purified PCR products are eluted from the surface of the membranes in small volumes (down to 20 μ l), giving eluates with high concentrations of DNA. It is possible to process PCR sample volumes up to 150 μ l using either a manual or fully automated procedure. PCR products are typically purified with a recovery of 80–95%.

Protocol taken from the Handbook of QIAGEN

This protocol is for purification of up to 96 PCR samples in parallel using a manual procedure.

- The use of MinElute 96 UF PCR Purification Plates requires a suitable vacuum manifold, e.g., the QIAvac Multiwell Unit, cat. no. 9014579.
- A multichannel pipet facilitates handling of PCR samples.
- For elution of DNA from MinElute 96 UF PCR Purification Plates, use of a microplate shaker is recommended. Alternatively, purified DNA can be dissolved by pipetting samples up and down 20 times.
- Deionized water (used for the optional wash step) and elution buffer must be supplied by the user.

Calibrating a microplate shaker for DNA elution

Calibrate a microplate shaker by following the steps below.

- Use a 96-well polystyrene microplate with 300 μ l round-bottom wells, e.g., 96-Well Microplates RB (24), QIAGEN cat. no. 19581.
- Add 200 μ l of a colored aqueous solution (e.g., bromophenol blue)*, to two wells.
- Place the 96-well plate on a microplate shaker.
- Set the speed to the lowest level and slowly increase the speed of the shaker. Ensure that the plate is fixed securely on top of the shaker.
- The recommended shaking speed for elution is the maximum speed at which no liquid is splashed out of the wells.

Purification procedure

- 1 Prepare the vacuum manifold according to the supplier's instructions. Place a waste tray inside the base of the manifold.
- 2 Place the MinElute 96 UF PCR Purification Plate on top of the vacuum manifold.
- 3 Pipet the PCR samples onto the MinElute 96 UF PCR Purification Plate.

Note: Processing PCR sample volumes larger than 150 μ l may lead to increased processing time and incomplete primer removal.

Apply a vacuum and maintain at –800 mbar for 5 min or until the wells are completely dry. Switch off vacuum source.

Note: If the PCR volume exceeds 50 μ l, a longer vacuum time is needed. Apply the vacuum until all wells are dry. Approximately 5 min of vacuum application are needed for each 50 μ l PCR volume.

- 4 **Optional: Add 50 μ l deionized water to each well, apply a vacuum, and maintain at –800 mbar for 5 minutes or until the wells are completely dry. Switch off vacuum source.**

Note: The purity of the DNA obtained after elution is sufficient for most applications without this wash step being required. If a higher purity is needed for a specific application, this step should be carried out.

- 5 Carefully remove the MinElute 96 UF PCR Purification Plate from the vacuum manifold.
- 6 Carefully tap the MinElute 96 UF PCR Purification Plate on a stack of clean absorbent paper to remove any liquid that might remain on the bottom of the plate.

- 7 **Add 20 μ l deionized water to each well.** DMSO (50% v/v)*, 3 x SSC*, and EB (10 mM Tris-Cl, pH 8.5)* or similar buffers can be used instead of water for elution.
- 8 **Elute DNA according to step 8a or 8b.**
 - 8a. **Shake the MinElute 96 UF PCR Purification Plate on a microplate shaker for 2 min at the recommended speed (see “Calibrating a microplate shaker for DNA elution”).**
Note: Ensure that the MinElute 96 UF PCR Purification Plate is fixed securely on top of the shaker.
 - 8b. **Alternatively, purified DNA may be dissolved by pipetting samples up and down 20 times.**
- 9 **Recover the purified PCR product by pipetting the eluate out of each well.** For easier recovery of the eluates, the plate can be held at a slight angle.

Figure 3. Purification procedure using MinElute 96 UF PCR Purification.

6. Nested PCR products quantification, normalization and pooling

This step requires three parts:

- Part I** Quantification of Nested PCR product concentration
- Part II** Diluting Nested PCR products in PCR water to a **15 ng/ μ L** solution.
- Part III** Nested PCR products pooling.

Protocol for Quant-iT PicoGreen® dsDNA quantification

This protocol uses the Quant-iT PicoGreen ® dsDNA kit (**Thermo Fisher Scientific**), which has been optimized to quantify dsDNA within a range of 150 ng (in a 200ul solution) to 2.34 ng (in a 200ul solution). The luminescence of PicoGreen is measured by a plate reader with the excitation of ~485nm and emission of ~530 nm.

Consumables

Table 7. Quant-iT PicoGreen Consumables

Item	Quantity	Storage
200X Quant-iT PicoGreen®	0.5 μ l per sample	2° to 8°C
20X TE buffer (10mM, pH 8.0), sterile filtered	5 μ l per sample	Room temperature
PCR / MilliQ water	200 μ l per sample	Room temperature
DNA stock [100ng/ μ L]	2 μ l per run	2° to 8°C

Equipment

- 96-well round bottom plate (black)
- Plate seal
- Well calibrated pipettes
- Multichannel pipette
- Reservoir
- Spectrophotometer (Excitation 485 nm; Emission 535 nm)

Preparation

- Create a 1X solution of 20X TE buffer and PCR / MilliQ water before you start.
- If the PCR products were stored at -20°C, let them equilibrate at room temperature for 15 - 30 min. Spin them down at 900 g x 1 min.
- Remove **PicoGreen® solution** from the fridge and bring to **room temperature and mix well!**
- PicoGreen® is a light-sensitive reagent →protect from light!

Procedure

- 1 Calculate volume of reagents needed for the number of samples adding 10% extra. Enter number of samples below (including standard curve).

200 μ L 1X TE /well	\times _____ wells	= _____ μ L 1X TE total volume
_____ 1X TE total volume	\div 20	= _____ μ L 20X TE buffer
_____ μ L 1X TE total volume	- _____ μ L 20X TE buffer	= _____ μ L PCR H ₂ O
100 μ L 1X PicoGreen /well	\times _____ wells	= _____ μ L 1X PicoGreen total vol
_____ 1X PicoGreen μ L total vol	\div 200	= _____ μ L 200X PicoGreen
_____ μ L 1X PicoGreen total vol	- _____ μ L 200X PicoGreen	= _____ μ L 1X TE buffer

- 2 **Prepare a standard curve.** In Eppendorf tubes, aliquot 1X TE buffer volume following the table instructions. Add 2 μ L of DNA stock solution to the first tube, which contains 198 μ L TE buffer; this will be the standard S1. Transfer 20 μ L from S1 to the tube labelled as S2, and continue till tube S4. The S5 tube is blank, so no DNA is required.

Table 8. Pipetting scheme of the standard curve (plate column 1)

Standard	DNA stock volume (μ L) ¹	1x TE buffer (μ L)	Volume transferred from the previous dilution	Tube[DNA] (ng/ μ L)	Final concentration after Picogreen is added in the assay (ng/ μ L)
S1	4	196	-	2	1
S2		180	20	0.2	0.1
S3		180	20	0.02	0.01
S4		180	20	0.002	0.001
S5		180	-	Blank	Blank

¹ DNA stock concentration is 100ng/ μ L

- 3 Transfer 100 μ L from each standard curve tube to the first column of plate.
- 4 Transfer **99 μ L of 1X TE buffer** to each well (**except** wells A1-E1).
- 5 Add **1 μ L PCR product** to each well and mix well (**except** wells A1-E1).
- 6 Add **100 μ L 1X PicoGreen** to each well. Protect the plate from light \rightarrow cover with foil.
- 7 Incubate plate at room temperature for 15 min on the plate shaker.
- 8 **Measure the fluorescence in Chameleon reader using the filters for excitation: 435 nm, and emission: 535 nm.** For measurement, follow the plate reader instructions.
- 9 **For calculations of DNA concentration, estimate the slope and intercept of the standard curve.** See Figure 4 for an example.

Standard curve	
DNA (ng/mL)	Fluorescence
1000	746159
100	64404
10	7246
1	621
0	0

Figure 4. Example of a standard curve for calculating DNA concentration. **Left panel:** DNA concentration of standards (ng/mL) and corrected fluorescence. **Right panel:** Linear curve and linear regression equation derived from Standard DNA concentrations and corresponding corrected fluorescence.

- Estimate the linear regression equation using the 5 points standard curve. Calculate the corrected fluorescence by subtracting the Blank fluorescence to all samples. Sum the slope to the corrected fluorescence and multiply the intercept. Do not forget to multiply by 200 (dilution factor).

PCR amplicons normalization at 15 ng/μL

This protocol aims to dilute the Nested PCR products at 15 ng/μL.

Figure 5. Schematic representation of PCR amplicon normalization. The left plate represents a PCR plate with wells containing different PCR yields/ concentration. The right plate represents a PCR plate with well containing homogenous DNA concentration after normalization.

Procedure

- Calculation:** In this example, the PCR product volume to pipet is fixed to 15 μL. To calculate the volume of PCR water, write the DNA concentration (ng/μL) in the excel template (Figure 6). The PCR product volume can change; this will depend on the volume available after PCR purification. Pipetting volumes ≥ 10uL it is recommended.

			Normalization			Pooling
End Time:			Dilution vol	DNA vol (uL)	H2O (uL)	Vol for 120 ng
Sample	Marker	Sample ID	DNA conc	→ 15.0		
A1	Chr11	AR-002-0	107.8825	15	92.9	8
B1		AR-064-0	79.82261	15	64.8	8
C1		AR-105-0	90.50084	15	75.5	8

Figure 6. Snapshot of excel template used for calculation of PCR water needed to dilute PCR products to 15ng/μL.

- The template uses the following formula:

$$H2O (\mu L) = \left(\frac{[DNA \frac{ng}{\mu L}] * 15\mu L}{15 \frac{ng}{\mu L}} \right) - 15\mu L$$

- After calculating the required volume of PCR water, in the Pre-PCR area, transfer the required volume of PCR water in each well like the plate layout example below (Figure 7).

H2O													
Ch11	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
A	93	68	110	76	115	119	71	85	114	6	200	113	
B	65	123	132	74	94	151	125	23	88	123	126	147	
C	76	2	88	107	7	136	6	108	123	179	127	75	
D	38	1	99	116	67	13	11	96	31	106	99	79	
E	-3	51	83	73	5	138	121	15	117	82	26	113	
F	0	67	79	7	83	120	99	71	68	69	93	79	
G	71	76	68	67	71	85	72	144	100	84	97	67	
H	67	88	97	113	92	89	82	149	73	67	117	54	

Figure 7. Template used as a visual aid of pipetting needed volume (μL) of PCR water to dilute PCR products to $15\text{ng}/\mu\text{L}$.

In the example, pink cells denote wells where DNA concentration is insufficient. **N.B.** If the yield of the library PCR is insufficient to get $15\text{ng}/\mu\text{L}$, do not add PCR water but PCR product.

- 3 With a multichannel pipet, add $15\ \mu\text{L}$ of PCR product to the corresponding wells and mix by pipetting up and down.
- 4 Centrifuge at $900 \times g$ at 20°C for 1 minute.

Pooling PCR amplicons

This protocol aims to pool equimolar amounts of amplicons per sample and reduce the workload in the Library PCR process (Figure 8). A good practice is to make 2 pools: one containing amplicons with good PCR efficiency, i.e. PCR products with visible bands in agarose electrophoresis for most of the samples; and another one containing amplicons with less PCR efficiency.

- 1 Using a multichannel, transfer the volume calculated to get 120ng of purified PCR product (e.g. $8\ \mu\text{L}$) from each sample to a new PCR plate. Use the tip box to guide your pipetting setup. The desired net DNA mass can change; this will depend on the initial DNA concentration of the PCR product of the majority of samples. This protocol has been optimized with 50 , 100 and 120ng of purified PCR product.

Figure 8. Schematic representation of amplicon pooling of 3 markers. Take 120ng of normalized PCR product from each plate.

7. Library Amplification or Index PCR

In this step, we execute a PCR to attach unique barcodes (indexes) to each sample. This step will allow multiplex up to 384 samples per sequencing run. The PCR is limited to 10 cycles and utilizes long fusion primers with P5/P7 adapter, Illumina index and overhang sequences in the backbone (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Schematic representation of Library (Index) primers. Individual or pool amplicons are subjected to limited PCR to attach unique dual combination of indexes in both amplicon ends.

Table 8. Sequence of fusion primer backbone for marker of chromosome 05

Name	Sequence
Fw_N501	AATGATACGGCGACCACCGAGATCT ACACTCTTTCCTACACGACGCTCTCC GATCTTAGATCGCGTGACCTATGAACTCAGGAGTC
Forward overhang (Linker F)	GTGACCTATGAACTCAGGAGTC
Index N501	TAGATCGC
Read sequencing primer (33 mer)-1	ACACTCTTTCCTACACGACGCTCTTCCGATCT
P5 (25 mer)	AATGATACGGCGACCACCGAGATCT

See the list of fusion primers that can be used for dual indexing (Table 9 and 10). Check the compatibility among the primers. Follow Illumina's recommendation, on page 3 (Document # 1000000041074 v06, Index Adapters Pooling Guide, Illumina, February 2019).

Table 9. Forward barcode i5 (Index 2)

Forward Design (Index 2)	Barcode/i5 (8 mer)
Fw_N501	TAGATCGC
Fw_N502	CTCTCTAT
Fw_N503	TATCCTCT
Fw_N504	AGAGTAGA
Fw_N505	GTAAGGAG
Fw_N506	ACTGCATA
Fw_N507	AAGGAGTA
Fw_N508	CTAAGCCT
Fw_AF037	CCGAAGTA
Fw_AF048	GAGCTGAA
Fw_AF051	GCGAGTAA
Fw_AF064	TGAAGAGA
Fw_AF067	TGGTGGTA
Fw_AF068	TTCACGCA
Fw_AF077	AGCACCTC
Fw_AF083	CAAGGAGC

Table 10. Reverse barcode i75 (Index 2)

Reverse Design (Index 1)	Barcode/i7 (8 mer)
Rv_N701	TAAGGCGA
Rv_N702	CGTACTAG
Rv_N703	AGGCAGAA
Rv_N704	TCCTGAGC
Rv_N705	GGACTCCT
Rv_N706	TAGGCATG
Rv_N707	CTCTCTAC
Rv_N708	CAGAGAGG
Rv_N709	GCTACGCT
Rv_N710	CGAGGCTG
Rv_N711	AAGAGGCA
Rv_N712	GTAGAGGA
Rv_AR003	ATGCCTAA
Rv_AR021	ACGCTCGA
Rv_AR027	AGTCACTA
Rv_AR028	ATCCTGTA
Rv_AR042	CGCATACA
Rv_AR045	CTGGCATA
Rv_AR049	GATAGACA
Rv_AR052	GCTAACGA
Rv_AR059	GTGTTCTA
Rv_AR062	TCCGTCTA
Rv_AR087	CCTAATCC
Rv_AR093	GACAGTGC

- 1 Arrange the Index 1 and 2 primers in a rack using the following arrangements:
 - a) Arrange Index 2 primer tubes (white caps) vertically, aligned with rows A through H.
 - b) Arrange Index 1 primer tubes (orange caps) horizontally, aligned with columns 1 through 12.

Figure 10. Scheme of indexing primers setup of TruSeq Index Plate. A Index 2 primers (white caps). B Index 1 primers (orange caps). C 96-well plate. In the case of fusion primers, arrange the Index adaptors in the same way, and individually pipette each adaptor into its corresponding well.

- 2 Place the 96-well PCR plate with the 5 μ L of resuspended PCR product DNA in the TruSeq Index Plate Fixture.
- 3 Set up the following reaction of DNA, Index 1 and 2 primers, 5x KAPA HiFi HotStart Mix, and PCR Grade water.

Table 11. Library Seq Master Mix

Library Seq Master Mix			
<i>Library Seq Master Mix</i>	Volume	X samples * 1.1	Final [conc]
<i>H₂O</i>	13.75 μ L		
<i>5X KAPA HiFi Buffer Fidelity</i>	5.00 μ L		1 x
<i>dNTP (10 mM)</i>	0.75 μ L		0.3 mM
<i>KAPA HiFi HotStart (1U/μL)</i>	0.5 μ L		0.02 units
Total*	20.0 μL		
<i>F Primer (5 μM)</i>	1.25 μ L ^a		0.25 μ M
<i>R Primer (5 μM)</i>	1.25 μ L ^b		0.25 μ M
Add			
gDNA	2.5 μ L/well		
TOTAL	25.0 μL		

Thermal cycling conditions	
95°	3:00 min
98°	0:20 min
65°	0:15 min
72°	0:45 min
72°	2:00 min
4°	∞

10 X

*: If you do not have a multicombed pipet (Eppendorf): Use a monochannel pipet and transfer 165 μ L of Master Mix in a PCR tubes strip (8), then use a multichannel to pipetting 20 μ L in each well.

^a: Dilute the stock primers from 100 μ M to 10 μ M, then a 2-fold dilution to get 5 μ M. To get the final volume of primer at 5 μ M, multiply 14 times the volume per well. Place the total volume in a well of a PCR tube strip (mimicking the figure #). Use a multichannel pipet to dispense 1.25 μ L.

b: Dilute the stock primers from 100 μM to 10 μM , then a 2- fold dilution to get 5 μM . To get the final volume of primer at 5 μM , multiply 10 times the volume per well. Place the total volume in a well of a PCR tube strip (mimicking the figure #). Use a multichannel pipet to dispense 1.25 μL .

4 Use a playout like this example:

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
A	N502									
B	N503									
C	N504									
D	N505									
E	N506									
F	N507									
G	N508									
H	AF037									

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
A	N701	N702	N703	N704	N705	N706	N707	N708	N709	N710
B	N701	N702	N703	N704	N705	N706	N707	N708	N709	N710
C	N701	N702	N703	N704	N705	N706	N707	N708	N709	N710
D	N701	N702	N703	N704	N705	N706	N707	N708	N709	N710
E	N701	N702	N703	N704	N705	N706	N707	N708	N709	N710
F	N701	N702	N703	N704	N705	N706	N707	N708	N709	N710
G	N701	N702	N703	N704	N705	N706	N707	N708	N709	N710
H	N701	N702	N703	N704	N705	N706	N707	N708	N709	N710

- 5 Centrifuge at $900 \times g$ at 20°C for 1 minute.
- 6 Cover the plate with Microseal 'A'.
- 7 Perform PCR on a thermal cycler using the corresponding program (Table 11)
- 8 If you choose to continue, proceed to PCR Clean-up 2

SAFE STOPPING POINT. If you do not immediately proceed to Library Quantification on page 27, seal plate with an adhesive seal and store it at 2° to 8°C for up to a week.

8. Library Quantification, Normalization and Pooling

Library Quantification

Follow the protocol of DNA measurement by PicoGreen as described on page 17.

Library Normalization at 20 ng/ μ L

Follow the protocol of DNA normalization, as described on page 19.

Library pooling

One hundred (100) ng of DNA/sample are pooled into a single Eppendorf tube/library.

- 1 Label each tube with the name of amplicons pooled.
- 2 Using a monochannel pipet, transfer 5 μ L from each sample to the assigned Eppendorf tube. Use the tip box to guide your pipetting setup. Consider pooling 40 samples max per tube.

Figure 11. Schematic representation of library pooling. One hundred (100) ng of DNA/sample are pooled into a single Eppendorf tube.

9. Pool purification, quantification and normalization

This step requires three parts:

- Part I** Pool purification with magnetic beads
- Part II** Quantification of fragment size and concentration to determine library concentration in nanomolar (nM)
- Part III** Diluting your final library in fresh 10 mM Tris pH 8.5 to a **20 nM** solution.

Pool purification

This protocol can be used to generate DNA fragment libraries with a certain size range or to narrow fragment-size distribution (300 - 500 bp). Primer dimers and non-desired PCR products are discarded.

The method is called double size selection because both smaller and larger fragments can be removed. The first step of DNA-beads mix enables binding of all DNA fragments longer than 500 bp. The beads with the unwanted larger DNA fragments are discarded (right side selection). The supernatant, which contains DNA fragments shorter than 500 bp, is transferred to a new tube to perform the second size selection step (left side selection): More bead suspension is added to the supernatant so that DNA fragments longer than 300 will be bound. After discarding the supernatant, DNA fragments within the desired size range are eluted.

Consumables

Table 12. Purification consumables

Item	Quantity	Storage
80% Ethanol (non-denatured)	0.5 µl per sample	2° to 8°C
Elution buffer (10mM Tris-HCl (pH 8.0))	5 µl per sample	Room temperature
NucleoMag® NGS Clean-up and Size Select KIT	200 µl per sample	Room temperature
T-200		Room temperature

Equipment

- 96-well magnetic separation system
- 96-well 300µL round bottom plate
- Well calibrated pipettors
- Vortex mixer
- Separation plate for magnetic beads separation (e.g. 96-well 0.3 mL microtiterplate (Elution Plate U-bottom))
- Plate seal

Preparation:

- Remove the NucleoMag® NGS Bead Suspension from the refrigerator and bring to room temperature for 30 min.
- **Mix** magnetic beads **well** before use (homogenous solution!!)

! Calculate the volume of magnetic beads/well before starting the procedure

Note: A ratio of 0.55 magnetic beads to DNA corresponds to 8.25µL magnetic beads and 15µL sample. A ratio of 0.25 magnetic beads to DNA corresponds to 3.75µL magnetic beads and 15µL sample.

Procedure

A Remove unwanted larger DNA fragments

- 1 Vortex the NucleoMag® NGS Bead suspension well until it appears **homogeneous in colour!**
- 2 Add ___µL of well-dispersed bead suspension to each well.
- 3 Add ___µL of DNA sample (the volume ratio of bead suspension to sample is ___).
- 4 Mix by pipetting up and down **10 times**.
- 5 Incubate at room temperature for 5 min.
- 6 Separate the magnetic beads against the side of the wells by placing the 96-well plate on the magnetic separator.
- 7 Wait **at least 5 min** until all the beads have been attracted to the magnets or until the **liquid** appears **clear**.
- 8 Transfer the supernatant into the well of a new plate and discard the beads that contain the unwanted large fragments.

B Remove unwanted smaller DNA fragments

- 9 Vortex the NucleoMag® NGS Bead suspension well until it appears **homogeneous in colour!**
- 10 Add ___µL of well-dispersed bead suspension to each well containing supernatants from step 1 (the total volume ratio of binding buffer and bead suspension to the original sample is now 0.8 (e.g. 55 µL and 25 µL to 100 µL).
- 11 Adjust the pipette to 200 µL and **mix by pipette** up and down 10 times.
- 12 Incubate at **room temperature** for **at 5 min**.
- 13 Separate the magnetic beads against the side of the wells by placing the 96-well plate on the magnetic separator.
- 14 Wait **at least 5 min** until all the beads have been attracted to the magnets or until the **liquid** appears **clear**.
- 15 Remove and discard the supernatant by pipetting.

Note: Do not disturb the attracted beads while aspirating the supernatant. Pipet supernatant from the opposite side of the well.

C 1st wash with 80 % ethanol

- 16 **Leave** 96-well plate **on the magnetic stand** during the washing step.
- 17 Add **200 µL** 80 % ethanol without disturbing the pellet.
- 18 Incubate at **room temperature** for **at least 30 sec**.
- 19 Carefully remove and discard the supernatant by pipetting.

D 2nd wash with 80 % ethanol

- 20 **Leave** 96-well plate **on the magnetic stand** during the washing step.
- 21 Add **200 µL** 80 % ethanol without disturbing the pellet.
- 22 Incubate at **room temperature** for **at least 30 sec**.
- 23 Carefully remove and discard the supernatant by pipetting.

Note: remove supernatant completely, including residual droplets.

E Dry the beads

- 24 **Leave** the 96-well plate **on the magnetic stand**.
- 25 Incubate **at room temperature** for **5–15 min** in order to allow the remaining traces of alcohol to evaporate.

Note: Allow the pellet to dry sufficiently so that there are no visible droplets of the supernatant at the bottom of the wells. Do not overdry beads. Yield may decrease since longer DNA fragments will elute slower.

F Elute DNA fragment library

- 26 **Remove the 96-well plate** from the magnetic stand.
- 27 Add **20 µL elution buffer** and **resuspend** the pellet **by pipetting** up and down **10 times** or by shaking (e.g., at 1100 rpm using an Eppendorf Thermomixer).
- 28 Incubate the separation plate at **room temperature** for **2–5 min**.

Note: 10 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8) or H₂O can be used as elution buffer.

- 29 Separate the magnetic beads against the side of the wells by placing the 96-well plate on the magnetic stand.
- 30 Wait **at least 5 min** until all the beads have been attracted to the magnets or until the **liquid** appears **clear**.
- 31 Transfer the supernatant containing the purified DNA fragments to a new 96-well plate.
- 32 DNA can be stored at 4°C.

Library Quantification

Follow the protocol of DNA measurement by PicoGreen as described on page 17.

Agilent Technologies Agilent D5000 ScreenTape System

This SOP format was adapted from the Agilent D5000 ScreenTape System Quick Guide protocol from Agilent Technologies.

Consumables

Table 12. TapeStation Consumables

Item	Quantity	Storage
Sample Buffer	10 µl per sample	2° to 8°C
D5000 Ladder	1 µl	2° to 8°C
ScreenTape	Holds 16 samples per tape	2° to 8°C+

Prepare TapeStation System D5000

- Launch the 2200 TapeStation Controller Software.
- Load single D5000 ScreenTape device and loading tips into the 2200 TapeStation instrument.

Sample Preparation D5000 ScreenTape Assay

- 1 Allow reagents to equilibrate at room temperature for 30 minutes.
- 2 Vortex mix before use.

- 3 Prepare ladder by mixing 10 μ l D5000 Sample Buffer (green lid) with 1 μ l D5000 Ladder (yellow lid) in a tube strip.
- 4 Prepare the sample by mixing 10 μ l D5000 Sample Buffer (green lid) with 1 μ l DNA sample in different tube strips.
- 5 Spin down, then vortex using IKA vortexer and adaptor at 2000 rpm for 1 minute.
- 6 Spin down to position the sample at the bottom of the tube.

Sample Analysis

- 7 Load samples into the 2200 TapeStation instrument
- 8 Select the required samples on the 2200 TapeStation Controller Software.
- 9 Click Start and specify a filename with which to save your results (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Representative results of analysis on D5000 ScreenTape® . A. Electrophoresis migration of final pool (red arrow). **B.** Electropherogram showing size distribution of final pool (average size 675 bp, range: 200 – 1000 bp).

Final library dilution at 20 nM

Procedure

- 1 Calculate the library molarity using the following formula:

$$\text{Concentration in nM} = \left(\frac{\left[\text{concentration in } \frac{\text{ng}}{\mu\text{L}} \right] * (10^6)}{\left(660 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}} \right)} \right) \times (\text{average library size})$$

- 2 Calculate the DNA volume and TE buffer.

$$\text{DNA } (\mu\text{L}) = \left(\frac{20 \text{ nM}}{\text{Concentration in nM}} \right) \times 100 \mu\text{L}$$

- 3 TE buffer volume is calculated by subtracting 100 μL - DNA volume μL . Use the excel template to calculate volumes.

Prepare final amplicon library

- 4 Pool the different sample pools. The volume of each normalized sample pool in the final amplicon library depends on the total number of pooled samples/pool.
- 5 To achieve equal sequence read coverage for all pooled markers/sample, the volume of the different sample pools has to be adjusted according to the sample pool with the least number of total samples that were pooled.

Table 13. Normalization of Final Amplicon library

Plate magnetic beads	Pool	sample number #amp	amplicon	total volume pool	volume magnetic bead	elution volume	picogram n (ng/ μL)	bp	nM (pool)	Dilution factor			pool volume for final library	comment	volumes taken 5 times from each samples
										10	volume sample(μL)	Volume buffer TE(μL)			
Solomon 1	Pool1	Pool1	32	160	88	20	23.8628	362	99.8777	9.98777	1.00	9.00	1.00		5
	Pool1	Pool1	32	160	88	20	23.0994	362	96.6826	9.66826	1.03	8.97	1.00		5
	Pool1	Pool1	32	160	88	20	29.9743	362	125.457	12.5457	0.80	9.20	1.00		5
	Pool2	Pool2	32	160	88	20	14.4732	362	60.5778	6.05778	1.65	8.35	1.00		5
	Pool2	Pool2	32	160	88	20	14.2128	362	59.4877	5.94877	1.68	8.32	1.00		5
	Pool2	Pool2	32	160	88	20	12.8387	362	53.7365	5.37365	1.86	8.14	1.00		5
	Pool3	Pool3	32	160	88	20	6.37697	362	26.6908	2.66908	3.75	6.25	1.00		5
	Pool3	Pool3	32	160	88	20	7.24812	362	30.337	3.0337	3.30	6.70	1.00		5
	Pool3	Pool3	32	160	88	20	13.1261	362	54.9394	5.49394	1.82	8.18	1.00		5